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Characteristics of the Tourist Offerings of Cittaslow in Spain and Africa

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ABSTRACT

While studies on slow tourism exist, research that employs a territorial perspective to investigate whether local governments in slow destinations are promoting their tourism offerings as slow, responsible, and sustainable is not common. Drawing on the theoretical principles of the international cittaslow network regarding what slow tourism should entail, this study analyses, using various tools, some characteristics of the 12 cittaslow locations in Spain and 2 in Africa. Evidence is sought to determine whether the dissemination of their territorial resources on their official websites aligns with the philosophical principles of the network. The results indicate that the majority should improve their dissemination efforts to highlight their status as slow destinations. Finally, a practical suggestion is made to encourage them to promote themselves as slow, responsible, and sustainable tourist destinations without incurring additional costs.

KEYWORDS

Slow tourism; sustainable tourism; Cittaslow; official websites; tourist resources; ODS12

Introduction

Studies on the tourism industry have revealed that it constitutes one of the major socio-economic drivers at the international level, with positive implications for addressing some of the significant issues faced by poor countries. Additionally, it is highlighted as one of the activities that generate significant negative impacts, demonstrating that sustainability remains one of the primary concerns today. The Sustainable Tourism Charter led both the UNWTO (1995) and the United Nations to recognize the need to implement the "Global Code of Ethics for Tourism" (Naciones Unidas, 2001), despite its 10 articles being non-binding. Alongside this, there is an attempt at conceptual clarification by stating that it is tourism that "fully takes into account its current and future economic, social, and environmental impacts, addressing the needs of visitors, the industry, the environment, and host communities" (UNWTO, 2004). Despite this, tourism is explicitly addressed in only two of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (8 and 12), in two targets (8.9 and 12.b) out of the 169 established, and in 5 indicators out of the 232 for monitoring, although its capacity to influence all of them is well recognized.

In the current academic community, there is no shortage of researchers who clearly deem it unsustainable, particularly when it occurs on a massive scale (Boluk et al., 2021; Cheer, 2020; Everingham & Chassagne, 2020; Hall, 2019; Scott et al., 2016). This perspective has led some to propose solutions related to degrowth (Andriotis, 2014, 2018; Hall, 2009, 2010). Ultimately, academia is demonstrating significant interest in promoting the sustainability of this industry (Ruhanen et al., 2015, 2019), emphasizing, among others, the studies of Butler (1999), Honey (2008), Goodwin (2016), and Sharpley (2020). Of particular interest are debates on whether achieving sustainability is feasible within the current economic system (Andriotis, 2018; Higgins-Desbiolles et al., 2019). There is a lack of consensus on the various ways to produce/redistribute the economic benefits derived from

the valorization of local resources, as well as on the impact measures to mitigate existing social gaps should have (Cole & Morgan, 2010). Additionally, it is necessary to address the unequal urgency given to reducing the negative socio-environmental impacts of mass tourism, known as overtourism (Capocchi et al., 2019; Colomb & Novy, 2016; Mansilla & Milano, 2018; Milano, 2018).

Non-profit organizations are also becoming involved in their implementation. This is exemplified by the international network of Cittaslow, which originated to expand the Slow Food philosophy in Italy, where Paolo Saturnini established an association in the small Tuscan town called Chianti in 1999. Since then, it has expanded to reach a current total of 297 Cittaslow, distributed across 33 countries.

The fact that the network includes among its objectives the promotion of sustainable development and tourism in cities around the world presents an interesting opportunity to deepen our understanding of how local governments are attempting to implement it in both the Global North and South, in developed and developing countries, in areas where Anglo-Saxon or Latin cultures predominate, and in population centers with varying productive specializations and demographic trends, both increasing and decreasing. Specifically, comparing how Spanish and African destinations promote Slow Tourism is of great interest. We need to expand our understanding of how they foster tourism in general and sustainable tourism in particular. Moreover, it is essential to explore whether factors such as spatial location (coastal/inland), differences in economic and demographic dynamism, the educational level of their inhabitants, and the various ways local populations participate in common goals, influence how their official websites disseminate the seven major groups of attributes that the network itself considers essential for characterizing a slow, responsible, and sustainable tourist destination.

This interest is further justified by the audacity of the leaders of the international network to present a proposal to the European Parliament to promote sustainability values in European cities (Spanish Network of Cittaslow).

However, the scientific community needs to gain a deeper and clearer understanding of, among others, the following questions: What does this network understand by sustainable tourism? Are the messages they disseminate on their websites to promote tourism consistent with the Slow philosophy? Is their method of promoting their tourism offerings online homogeneous? Are they effectively communicating their achievements in advancing sustainable tourism?

To address these issues, we have structured the study into the following sections. The first section discusses the challenges in defining slow tourism and introduces Cittaslow, a global network promoting sustainable practices among residents and visitors.

It includes literature review of member cities, covering their membership timeline, objectives, methods, and conclusions. The second section outlines the research procedures, while the third presents the findings. The fourth section provides discussions and conclusions. The final section suggests future research directions and ways to better promote sustainable tourism in slow cities.

Literature review

Conceptual precisions

The bibliographic analysis of slow tourism conducted by Mavric et al. (2021) demonstrates its expansion, primarily since the beginning of the twenty-first century. Studies conducted in Europe are the most numerous and share the common goal of characterizing slow tourism and exploring its potential as an alternative to mass tourism. Although it aspires to be a type of sustainable tourism (Le Busque et al., 2021), there is no consensus on its definition. An attempt to advance its conceptualization and interpretation has led to its incorporation into a framework where six pillars stand out, with the concept of slowness playing a prominent role in YouTube's slow travel vlogs (Manthiou et al., 2022). Thus, the

mentioned researcher highlights the flexibility of the offer that characterizes it, the social commitment at the destination, the consumption of local products, the experiences provided by the destination, the high value attributed to it by tourists, and the opportunities it offers for experiencing the journey and the stay intensely.

Indeed, all of the above leads to over-consuming experiences while protecting everything that produces and maintains them, instead of over-consuming and/or massively using material resources, which increase the negative impacts generated by our actions. The interest in making tourism a sustainable activity is growing, largely motivated by the increasing importance that demand places on quality of life, well-being, and “buen vivir” (Moore, 2012; Tu et al., 2022). However, this trend needs to be considered in a context where there is still much work to be done.

Sustainability is increasingly regarded by entrepreneurs as a key indicator for enhancing the quality of their offerings, social responsibility, and the competitiveness of their businesses (Calisto et al., 2021). There are also significant groups, such as the Virgin Group with the “Virgin Voyages” initiative or Airbnb, that are striving through mass media to promote themselves as advocates for sustainability in the tourism industry by reducing their carbon footprint. However, in the business sector, results still need significant improvement.

The importance that the general population places on promoting sustainability in their daily practices is also clearly insufficient (Lew, 2020), with tourists reacting very passively to the serious congestion problems experienced by major destinations (Woo et al., 2022). This ultimately increases cases of tourismphobia among the local population (Milano, 2018) and/or gentrification (Barrado-Timón & Hidalgo-Giralt, 2019). In conclusion, the number of slow tourists does not seem to be significant among European tourists overall (Lumsdon & McGrath, 2011).

Here, we will adopt a definition of slow tourism based on information provided by the official websites of the Cittaslow networks. Slow tourism is characterized as a form of sustainable, responsible, and high-quality tourism that promotes a leisurely lifestyle and the enjoyment of unique experiences for a limited number of visitors. This approach fosters lifestyles and tourism practices that respect local resources, which form the basis for future development, in contrast to mass, rapid consumption of imported industrial products and standardized services.

Slow tourism encourages respect, appreciation, and even the recovery of resources present in the natural, cultural, and social environment of each location. It also promotes the use of low-pollution means of transportation for both visitors and residents, as well as longer stays, with the aim of fostering deeper experiences that facilitate the exchange of ideas and the integration of visitors into community life.

Most of the main attributes of slow tourism mentioned above are collected by the Spanish Network of Cittaslow, Table 1.

The international Cittaslow network claims to promote slow tourism

Among the studies that theoretically could help advance our understanding of slow tourism is the analysis of the international Cittaslow network. It is known to be a network that establishes compliance requirements for adherence, as well as for achieving excellence (Cittaslow International Charter, 2023). Among its aspirations is to promote the culture of “buen vivir” through research, experimentation, and application of solutions for urban organization, favoring historical identity, protecting the environment, promoting social inclusion, and even the active participation of citizens.

There is evidence to assert (despite criticisms based on utopian ideals) that the Cittaslow network significantly promotes the improvement of the quality of life of its inhabitants and also of the tourists who visit them (Presenza et al., 2015a), enhancing underappreciated and underexploited resources (Dogrusoy & Dalgakiran, 2011). This is done in an attempt to provide an alternative to the living conditions that globalization is producing in the cities of the most developed countries, combating immediacy and fast, polluting transportation methods (Dickinson & Lumsdon, 2010).

Certification for joining the network requires surpassing more than 50% of the 73 criteria grouped into seven categories, enabling the implementation of a more sustainable tourism governance in the cities that achieve it (Presenza et al., 2015b). This seems to be evidenced, for example, by the revitalization that occurred in the city of Goolwa, as a result of increased collaboration among residents, visitors, and businesses in pursuit of accreditation (Park & Sangkyun, 2016). It is essential to ensure that tourism is sustainable in these cities, that the population becomes involved and perceives the benefits derived from it (Pekeryen & Kaplan, 2023), which

Table 1. Attributes of slow tourism according to the Spanish Cittaslow Network.

Attributes of slow tourism
1. Minimize negative social (a), economic (b) and environmental (c) impacts
2. Promote the generation of economic benefits for the local population (a) and improve the well-being of visitors (b)
3. Encourage the participation of tourism stakeholders (a) and businesses (b) in decision-making that affects tourism
4. Make positive contributions to the conservation of diverse natural (a) and cultural (b) heritage
5. Provide leisurely and enjoyable experiences for tourists through meaningful connections with local cultural (a), social (b) and environmental (c) traditions
6. Provide standardized access for all types of tourists
7. Foster respect and trust between tourists and local population

Source: Spanish Cittaslow Network. The authors

requires promoting interactions between the population and local resources (Hatipoglu, 2015) that enhance the identity of places and the sense of belonging of their populations (Ekinci, 2014).

It is also important to understand the main dimensions that influence tourists' decision-making regarding destinations to visit, to apply them to Cittaslow cities (Han et al., 2019) and to consider that differences between sustainable slow cities constitute an important factor in the decision of the place to visit (Ince et al., 2020). While the slow city model has been considered useful for promoting the development of small cities (Zadęcka, 2018), it is increasingly necessary to have indicators that allow for the evaluation of tourism in Cittaslow cities, to help improve their outcomes (Kim et al., 2022; Maroto et al., 2023).

Few studies on Spanish and African Cittaslow

Research on Cittaslow in Spain, South Africa, and Mozambique dates back to the early years of the twenty-first century. The Spanish Cittaslow network began to take shape in 2003, in response to an invitation from the international Cittaslow network to the municipality of Palafrugell (no longer a member of the network), which responded affirmatively. In the case of South Africa, Sedgfield joined the network in 2010. Matambo (Mozambique) submitted its application in 2020 and is currently a "Cittaslow in Progress" The first significant study was conducted by De Luis, A. (2011), who, after reviewing the slow philosophy, carried out a study of Spanish Cittaslow cities as a whole. Their analysis was based on in-depth, unstructured telephone interviews with tourism managers. They found, upon analyzing both the tourist supply and demand, that Spanish Cittaslow cities were not adhering to the principles of the Slow philosophy.

Morales and Méndez (2012) emphasize that the Spanish Cittaslow network constitutes a thematic network linked to its urban policies, aimed at achieving better positioning in the global market. Considering the vast amount of heritage resources in these cities, they believe there are many places that could potentially be part of the network and benefit from the development opportunities it offers.

Pink and Servon (2013), analyzing Spanish Cittaslow cities, concluded that the network framework does not provide a development model that can be applied to favor their regeneration. However, they believe it does enable local governments to better understand the importance and uniqueness of the resources in their city, through a model that helps them promote their improvement within the framework of current global processes.

Llussà (2015), analyzing tourism planning in the Costa Brava, considers the Cittaslow

phenomenon as a tool for the development of slow tourism, concluding that surprisingly, the involvement of municipal governments is almost nonexistent. They also state that the population is not aware that the cities are part of the network and that less than 50% of the established requirements are met. As a result, they conclude that the experience of the two Cittaslow cities in the province of Girona has not been very successful.

Servon and Pink (2016) argue that the emergence of Cittaslow is a reaction against globalization to try to avoid homogenization. Spanish Cittaslow cities are not homogenizing their production systems but adapting to both local and global markets simultaneously. Moreover, they believe that reinforcing their identities can pose risks, such as a limited influx of tourists that can negatively impact the territory.

Hernández-Mogollón et al. (2017) argue that traditional mass tourism is insufficient to meet new demands, questioning whether slow tourism is economically viable. Website analysis allows them to affirm that while there are multiple initiatives based on slowness, very few are truly slow tourism. The incipient situation of this type of tourism in Spain does not correspond to the country's significant tourism importance internationally.

Ruiz-Álvarez (2020) studies the development and implementation of the Local Tourism Plan for Quality of Life "Bubiión Slow". After evaluating the degree of implementation of the actions halfway through the execution period, they discover that there were delays due to "budgetary difficulties for socio-cultural and population participation, or the different regulations that sometimes complicate the implementation of the programs". Despite this, they consider the overall outcome to be positive.

Serrano-González et al. (2020), studying La Orotava (Tenerife, Canary Islands, Spain), conduct an analysis of the tourist destination based on focus groups, which identified the main weaknesses, strengths, threats, and opportunities to facilitate destination management and implement the requirements of this Cittaslow certification.

De Gracia and Jareño (2021) believe there is a high degree of compatibility between smart cities and slow cities despite their very different approaches. They show hope in participatory projects of Cittaslow driven in the Cittaslow of Begues, the commitment to the consumption of Km 0 products in shops and restaurants, as well as the use of electric transport. It would be beneficial to establish a dialogue between those responsible for promoting smart tourist municipalities and Cittaslow towns, as both networks aim to be innovative tourist destinations that seek to ensure the sustainable development of their territories. They share a common goal: fostering visitor interaction and integration with the environment, which would undoubtedly enhance the quality of the tourist experience and improve the quality of life for the local population. However, their philosophies are, at least theoretically, antagonistic. The philosophy behind the Cittaslow network involves a critique of the current capitalist system, while the Smart Tourist Destinations network aims to improve residents' quality of life by increasing the destination's competitiveness. Finally, Maroto et al. (2023), in a comparative analysis of the tourist supply activities disclosed on the official websites of the city councils of Spanish Cittaslow cities and the official tourism websites of those cities, concluded that although the 12 Spanish Cittaslow cities have a significant number of heritage resources, both historical and natural, only 30% of them leverage the uniqueness of being a Cittaslow to promote their tourism and demonstrate that they are promoting it to be slow, responsible, and sustainable.

In the case of South Africa, there are also very few studies focusing on slow tourism, when compared to those existing on small towns. We highlight two, one by Titus (2015) and especially those by Donaldson (2018a). The work by Titus (2015) highlights that knowledge of slow tourism in South Africa was scarce in those years and considers it necessary to address this gap through a proposed model of slow tourism based on the resources of the Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden.

The contribution of Donaldson's book (2018a) falls within this researcher's interest in the

characteristics of Small-Town Tourism in South Africa, leading him to meticulously study the case of the Cittaslow Sedgefield. Of particular interest is Chapter 5 (Donaldson, 2018b), where he asserts that it was a local elite that drove a series of actions that ultimately led to Sedgefield becoming Africa's first Cittaslow. Based on twenty in-depth interviews and guided by the principles of the charter, he demonstrates the differences in knowledge and opinion among the population about what this recognition as a Cittaslow entails, and also the different existing visions on which direction the city should take in the future.

Finally, as far as we know, there are no publications in indexed journals about Matambo in Mozambique, a circumstance that makes it difficult to conduct a detailed analysis.

As a result of the above, it is evident that research on Cittaslow in Spain and Africa is scarce, although the conclusions obtained include the main topics addressed in the international literature. The subject has been primarily studied by researchers with backgrounds in geography, economics, sociology, tourism, and even history. This accounts for the utilization of diverse perspectives, methods, and analytical techniques.

The absence of official sources has favored the use of in-depth interviews with key actors, or more recently, the information contained in the media or in the Cittaslow networks themselves. However, the available studies are limited in number, despite the importance of the topic. We need more research that compares Cittaslow from different countries, taking into account the particular geographic characteristics of each Cittaslow and the importance they place on disseminating what they are doing to promote sustainability. This justifies the present work.

In this context, it is necessary to test the following hypotheses:

1° The definition of Slow, responsible, and sustainable tourism aligns with what most scholars of sustainable tourism understand by this concept.

2° The tourism offerings promoted by Cittaslow on their websites are generally consistent with the Slow philosophy. They are primarily based on endogenous resources (natural, historical-artistic, etc.) but adapt to the socio-economic and cultural contexts of the regions in which they are located.

3° To promote their tourist attractions, Cittaslow uses websites with a wide range of technical characteristics.

4° Cittaslow could uniformly disseminate the efforts they are making to promote Slow tourism at a relatively low economic cost.

To enhance our understanding of this issue, the general objective of this study is, based on a general characterization of the 14 Cittaslow (the 12 from Spain and the 2 from Africa), to address the following question: Are there evidences that municipal governments are disseminating the principles of slow tourism, and specifically what the network understands by slow, responsible, and sustainable tourism? The specific objectives are to understand:

- What does the Cittaslow network understand by slow, responsible, and sustainable tourism?
- What are the general characteristics of the tourist offerings of the studied Cittaslow?
- Are the local governments of the studied Cittaslow promoting their tourism resources and products in a manner consistent with Slow philosophy?
- Could the Cittaslow uniformly disseminate, at no economic cost, the efforts they are making in favor of slow, respectful, and sustainable tourism?

Methodology

To better understand slow tourism in the Spanish and African Cittaslow, a literature review was conducted using the Scopus and Web of Science databases. Due to the scarcity of relevant information, additional searches were performed on Google Scholar and Dialnet (Figure 1). The study required a general characterization of the 14 analyzed Cittaslow, using data from national statistical services.

The tourist offerings were categorized based on information from the international and Spanish Cittaslow networks. While Sedgfield has a useful official website, information about Matambo is limited, requiring the use of indirect sources such as social media and data from the NGO Dignity, which supports its goal of becoming the second African Cittaslow. Official websites of municipal governments and tourism offices were also analyzed, as they are considered reliable and secure sources for potential tourists.

These websites were valued for providing official, up-to-date information on culture, history, attractions, and urban projects, as well as reflecting local policies. Official tourism websites are generally reliable, designed to promote cities with detailed and appealing information for visitors.

Figure 1. Methodological sequence followed in the research. Source: The authors.

Internet has not only become the primary channel for promoting tourist destinations (Buhalis, 2003; Buhalis & Law, 2008; Morrison, 2013) but also the main means by which the population gathers information about potential destinations to visit. It is crucial in decision-making and even for planning their tourist trips and stays (Buhalis & Law, 2008; Xiang & Gretzel, 2010).

To establish the categorization of Cittaslow based on the main resources their tourist offerings rely on, the classification of tourist attractions by categories by López-Olivares (2014) has been used for its simplicity and clarity. It differentiates them into:

1°. Natural or scenic attractions; 2°. Historical monuments, technical, ethnological, and artistic attractions; 3°. Craft and gastronomic attractions, and finally, 4°. Folklore and scheduled events.

These categories have been ordered according to their importance within each Citta- slow, following the criterion of the order in which the main resources appear on the web- sites. Consequently, it has been considered as a criterion that the website managers present the most important resources first to attract potential slow tourists and sub- sequently, others that are considered secondary.

The fact that the Spanish network has managed to synthesize seven groups of attri- butes of slow tourism, Table 1, has allowed us to try to verify that there is evidence of its diffusion on the official websites of the 14 Cittaslow.

These issues have been analyzed in two different ways.

The first method has been to carry out a semantic analysis (Feldman, 2013), using in this case the alyze.com tool. Semantic analysis through online software is a technique that uses computational tools to understand the meaning and relationship between words, phrases or paragraphs within a specific context. This analysis is based on natural language processing (NLP) algorithms that allow machines to interpret the meaning beyond the grammatical structure.

The second approach consisted of carrying out an exhaustive reading of the contents of the official websites, looking for evidence of the 7 groups of attributes mentioned above with the help of a table.

Results

General characterization of the studied Cittaslows

The 14 Cittaslows under study are distributed across three countries: Spain, South Africa, and Mozambique (Figure 2).

Spanish settlements boast a long history and rich archaeological and historical heritage, Sededfield, founded in 1929, has primarily served as a vacation destination for retired white populations from South Africa, maintaining its municipal indepen- dence until the early twenty-first century. Matambo, a recently established village in Mozambique, lacks electricity from the national grid and faces challenges with water supply and healthcare. Local leaders in Matambo have sought to improve the situation by collaborating with the NGO Dignity and the Cittaslow network. Additionally, food scarcity is a concern, especially for children, who often have only one meal a day.

Figure 2. Location of the Cittaslow in Spain and Africa. Source: The authors.

In the case of Spanish Cittaslow municipalities, their connection to the international network began with an invitation to Palafrugell, which later extended to other cities in Catalonia and the rest of Spain (Maroto et al., 2023). In Sedgefield, an elite group drove its acceptance as a Cittaslow, meeting the established requirements (Donaldson, 2018b). In Matambo, currently in the process of becoming a Cittaslow, the NGO Dignity Italy and its Mozambique branch have facilitated its candidacy and are leading community changes, promoting development projects based on sustainable endogenous resources, including providing drinking water funded by the 8xmille CEI – Sictm (Aldeia Dignity, 2020).

In summary, in the 14 Cittaslow municipalities we studied, it can be said that all, except Matambo, which is in the process of joining, are populations where residents have living conditions typical of developed countries. Although there are significant economic contrasts, their population has their basic needs of food, clothing, and shelter covered, as well as access to education, healthcare, and social services.

How has the demographic dynamics of Cittaslow municipalities changed since joining the network?

Understanding the demographic dynamics of Cittaslow municipalities since joining the network (Table 2) allows us to determine whether those facing depopulation issues are successfully improving their situation and if measures need to be taken in Cittaslow to prevent overcrowding at certain times of the year.

The Spanish Cittaslow municipalities that have experienced an increase in their population since joining the network are predominantly located on the Mediterranean coast and are economically much more dynamic than the rest. However, their demographic dynamics are similar to those of non-Cittaslow municipalities, which are also located on the Mediterranean coast. Belonging to the Cittaslow network does not explain their demographic evolution. Most inland Cittaslow municipalities are characterized by having a relatively low population, predominantly rural, with a demographic structure characterized by strong demographic aging, negative natural growth due to the lack of births, and an increase in mortality as a result of significant aging. Their population loss is not being offset by the arrival of immigrants.

Table 2. Some demographic and economic characteristics of Cittaslow.

Cittaslow	Country	Year of joining the network	Population in 2023	Annual average change until 2023	Businesses per 100 inhabitants 2023	Location Coastal or Inland
Artà		2021	8.208	1,4%	9,4	Coastal
Balmaseda		2015	7.593	-0,3%	5,3	Inland
Begues		2015	7.432	1,4%	3,0	Coastal
Begur		2007	4.216	0,2%	11,1	Coastal
Benabarre		2021	1.168	0,3%	6,4	Inland
Bubión		2018	309	0,5%	15,9	Inland
La Orotava		2018	42.454	0,3%	5,8	Coastal
Lekeitio		2008	7.143	-0,3%	4,9	Coastal
Morella		2015	2.492	-0,4%	13,0	Inland
Mungia		2008	17.882	0,8%	7,9	Inland
Pals		2007	2.539	0,0%	10,9	Coastal
Rubielos de Mora		2008	627	-1,4%	10,4	Inland
Sedgefield		2010	8.286 (in 2011)	No data. Growth.	Higher than similar nearby cities	Coastal
Matambo*		2011	5.000	No data. Growth.	Higher than similar nearby cities	Inland

Source: The authors

For Sedgefield, no official demographic data has been available since the 2011 census. However, indirect sources from official websites and data from the Greater Knysna municipality, to which it belongs, suggest recent positive trends in population and the economy. Sedgefield offers most essential shops and services, with good accessibility to the municipal capital, 25 km away, and other key cities.

Matambo, about 30 km from Tete's capital, lacks recent demographic data, but its population is estimated at 5,000, growing due to high fertility and a young demographic. Bishop Diamantino Antunes has described Matambo's residents as "the poorest among the poor," highlighting the urgent need for support (Dignity, 2022a). The NGO Dignity and the Cittaslow network are working to develop Matambo into a "progressing slow city" based on Cittaslow's quality standards (Dignity, 2022b). An inspection by the International Cittaslow Network in mid-2023 highlighted significant improvements in Matambo. Food security has increased with expanded agricultural production and irrigation. Craft production and transportation between settlements have improved, facilitating school access and promoting sustainable tourism. Additionally, the renovation of the Matambo Health Center has enhanced disease prevention and healthcare, particularly for pregnant women, childbirth, breastfeeding, and weaning (Aldeia Dignity, 2023).

Typification of Cittaslow municipalities based on the importance they give to their tourist resources

The analysis of the website of the Spanish Cittaslow network, in its tourism section, allows for typification following the classification proposed by López-Olivares (2014). The analysis of the Spanish Cittaslow network website, in its tourism section, allows for typification following the classification proposed by López-Olivares (2014) and the aforementioned criterion (Table 3).

The majority of municipalities with coastal areas do not present their beaches as the main attraction for tourists, which seems to be in line with the philosophy of slow tourism that aims to avoid becoming overcrowded destinations, characteristic of this tourist segment. Spanish Cittaslow municipalities that highlight their historical and artistic resources are predominant. These are cities with well-preserved medieval old towns, which have earned them the legal recognition of "Historic-Artistic Ensemble". Some of them also have the great advantage of being located in protected natural areas, such as Sierra Nevada National Park, Teide Natural Park, Montgrí

Natural Park, the Medes Islands, and Bajo Ter, among others. The multiple resources of interest in these cities have led to the design and promotion of festive activities, mainly related to their medieval history.

Sedgefield has grounded its identity in its distinctive environmental features, aligning with the vision of the Department of Environmental Affairs and Tourism for the Garden Route National Park, since its designation as a Slow Town in 2009. Information available on its official website, updated in 2022, reveals the early support from the Sedgefield Ratepayers and Residents Association for the Slow Town initiative. Their collective focus was on preserving the natural environment and considering this aspect in local development and infrastructure. This perspective is reinforced through its main promotional video and events such as the Sedgefield Slow Town Festival and a variety of activities, ranging from fishing to other less recreational options.

The case of Matambo is difficult to typify. Tourists visiting the area are primarily interested in assisting the Matambo community. They are voluntary members of the NGO Dignity who collaborate in the development project through scheduled activities. This includes literacy meetings, agricultural training, artistic education, craftsmanship, sports, hygiene, and health. The activities, organized by Mozambican trainers and aimed at children and youth, represent the first steps towards the creation of the multifunctional community center “Aldeia Dignity” (the village of dignity), key to guaranteeing the fundamental rights of children and adolescents. The project also receives support from the parish community of the Gran Madre di Dio parish in Rome (Aldeia Dignity, 2019).

Table 3. Typification of Cittaslow municipalities based on the importance with which they promote their resources.

Municipality	Tourist Attractions			
Artà	1	2	3	4
Balmaseda	2	1	4	3
Begues	1	2	4	3
Begur	1	2	4	3
Benabarre	2	1	3	4
Bubión	2	1	4	3
La Orotava	2	1	4	3
Lekeitio	4	2	3	1
Morella	2	4	3	1
Mungia	2	4	1	3
Pals	2	1	3	4
Rubielos de Mora	2	4	3	1
Sedgefield	1	4	3	2
Matambo*	4	3	2	1

Source: The authors based on the information contained on the website of the Spanish Cittaslow network and using the classification of tourist attractions ordered by categories established by López-Olivares (2014) (1.Natural or landscape; 2.Historical, monumental, technical, ethnological, and artistic; 3.Artisanal and gastronomic; 4.Folklore and programmed events).

Are the principles of slow tourism included in the official websites of Cittaslow municipalities?

The analysis with alyze.com allows us to affirm that the vast majority of cities do not promote their membership in the Cittaslow network. This assertion may seem contradictory to the observation that the logo of the network, which is a snail, appears in almost all of them. However, the fact that it is not prominently and easily visible, as well as its very limited presence, justifies this. Breaking this norm is the case of Bubi3n, where the terms “slow destination” and “slow tourism” are among the top five positions in weighted score of relationships between two terms present on the website. Morella also prominently advertises that it is an “official cittaslow,” ranking sixth, or “slow city” in 16th place. But it is especially the case of Sedgefield, where “slow town,” “Sedgefield slow,” and “slow festival” occupy the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd positions respectively, both on the municipal government’s website and on the official tourism website. Additionally, terms like “town festival” and “town garden” rank 5th and 6th.

For the rest of the Cittaslow municipalities, it can be asserted, through this type of analysis, that they do not place importance on being part of the network, as evidenced by their lack of significant promotion.

This does not imply that other terms related to the slow philosophy are not promoted on their websites; however, their presence is again quite limited. Faced with this reality, we have chosen to complement this analysis with another less quantitative and mechanistic one. We refer to the one based on a careful reading aimed at finding evidence of the seven issues that the Cittaslow network in Spain considers should favor slow tourism in Cittaslow municipalities. Our study has allowed us to demonstrate that these seven characteristics that should favor slow tourism are met in most of them (Table 4). While this assertion is formally correct, it is also true that in most cases, it does not seem to be due to their membership in the Cittaslow network, as similar terms are also found on the websites of many municipalities in their surroundings.

In the case of Spanish Cittaslow municipalities, three out of every four are characterized by including information that demonstrates their interest in promoting tourism in a leisurely manner. The rest of them do not do so explicitly, but their websites are highly attractive and mainly consist of images, videos, and minimal text, which are highly captivating and suggest values related to sustainability. This can be interpreted in several ways in the context of a city following the principles of the “slow” movement. According to Fullagar et al. (2012) and Filiopoulos and Poulaki (2023), this could be due to:

Predominance of sensory experience: Images capture the beauty of the natural environment, local architecture, and gastronomy, reflecting the importance of enjoying the environment through the senses.

Promotion of digital disconnection: By prioritizing images over text, the website encourages a quieter and more present lifestyle, in line with the values of the “slow” movement.

Table 4. Existence or absence of evidence on the websites of the Cittaslow municipalities regarding the seven major attributes that slow tourism (responsible and sustainable) must meet.

Official websites of the Cittaslow municipalities	Cittaslow logo	1		2		3		4		5		6	7	Observations
		a	b	c	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b		
Artà	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Good website to promote slow tourism..
Balmaseda	✓	-	-	✓	-	✓	-	-	✓	-	-	✓	-	Only one piece of information about being a Cittaslow at the time of admission.
Begues	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Very good website to promote slow tourism.
Begur	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Focuses on trying to evoke emotions in tourists
Benabarre Bubión	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Very recent admission. Actively working towards slow tourism.
La Orotava	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Embraces the “slow” philosophy by introducing tourists to the concept of good living and encouraging them to practice it.
Lekeitio	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Emphasizes slow values in commercial establishments.
Morella	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	No references. Some on Twitter.
Mungia	If it's about being one of the most beautiful towns in Spain, not Cittaslow	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Has not carried out any actions as a Cittaslow for years.
Mungia	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	The Mayor of Mungia has assumed the presidency of the Spanish network. Their website has improved information about the network.
Pals	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Good website to promote slow tourism.
Rubielos de Mora	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	High interest in promoting slow tourism
Sedgefield	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Good website to promote slow tourism..
Matambo*	✓	*There is no official website for Matambo. Information from the Cittaslow International website and the Dignity NGO website has been used https://www.dignitypeople.eu/matambo-citta-slow/												

Source: The authors based on the official websites of the Cittaslow municipalities.

Emphasis on simplicity and authenticity: The website conveys authenticity by presenting information visually, suggesting that meaningful experiences can be communicated without extensive text.

The official websites of Sedgefield can be considered the best among those studied for promoting slow tourism, although they also demonstrate a desire to attract people interested in practicing adventure sports such as paragliding, kitesurfing, wakeboarding, water skiing, and surfing. The websites of Sedgefield not only present the history of the city but also offer a wide range of slow activities, demonstrating an interest in beautifying and even protecting the town from actions that may alter its principles. Additionally, measures are in place to encourage visitors to engage in the life of the town and adopt the principles of the Slowtown. The voluntary work of the population working for the community is an excellent example of involvement, as well as the actions of charitable organizations in favor of the most vulnerable people, especially vulnerable children.

Matambo, without an official website, presents a unique case. Information from the Dignity NGO shows efforts to improve living conditions, with tourism not a short-term focus. However, ongoing projects attract workers and volunteers, creating a form of solidarity-based tourism. Due to the area's poverty, tourism's impact remains minimal, and no actions to reduce it have been noted. Yet, current measures support its development, positioning Matambo as an emerging Cittaslow municipality under the guidance of Dignity and the Cittaslow International network.

Discussion and conclusions

The theoretical analysis of what the Cittaslow network considers slow, responsible, and sustainable tourism allows us to affirm that this characterization is superior to most of the definitions found in the consulted literature. Furthermore, it can be argued that the issues it encompasses cover the six pillars outlined by Manthiou et al. (2022) for slow tourism: the flexibility of the offer that characterizes it, social commitment at the destination, consumption of local products, the experiences provided by the destination, the high value attributed by tourists, and the possibilities it offers for experiencing the journey and stay intensely. As a result, it can be said that the Cittaslow network is based on a definition of slow, responsible, and sustainable tourism that is consistent with the best definitions made by scholars in this field.

However, it is worth noting that there is no evidence that they promote tourism aimed at completely eliminating the impacts generated by tourism in Cittaslow. It seems that they settle for reducing them. Additionally, the websites of the studied Cittaslow cities do not state that they aim to avoid economic speculation or reduce visitor congestion. Ultimately, based on the available information, it can be asserted that they are not cities advocating for degrowth (Latouche, 2006) as a means to advance towards sustainability.

To properly understand the slow tourism of each city, it is necessary to first consider their characteristics and singularities, as well as the resources on which their tourism offer is based. It must be recognized that territories bear the impacts of tourism differently. Furthermore, in their location, in the characteristics of their physical environment, and in their historical evolution lie the keys that allow us to understand not only the importance of their resources, but also their potential and capacity to attract tourists.

On the other hand, exploring their current issues and aspirations allows us to understand the reasons that drove them to seek membership in the Cittaslow network.

Most of the slow cities studied here are located inland and have a small number of inhabitants, so they have made efforts to join the network as a strategy to economically revitalize their productive fabric through tourism and find solutions to their serious depopulation problems. Others have joined the network as a means of differentiation from other competing destinations and to advance the protection of their heritage, while raising awareness of sustainability values. In all cases, without exception, the driving forces have been members of the local government. In the vast majority, not all residents participate or significantly influence their development as a Cittaslow. This statement seems to have exceptions in smaller towns, such as Bubi3n, where citizen participation has been and continues to be very high.

Cultural tourism based on their historical heritage predominates in them. Even where there is the possibility of developing the tourism segment based on sun and beach, they are not the sole attractions, nor are they the most promoted in the vast majority of cases. This study verifies that the majority of Cittaslows take into account the seven aspects promoted for slow tourism. However, some Cittaslows do not sufficiently disclose their affiliation with the network or consistently promote the slow philosophy. Additionally, several cities meet the criteria without being affiliated with the network, and few make efforts to promote sustainability awareness among residents and visitors.

The above can be interpreted as local governments have strived to join the Cittaslow network with the clear intention of purchasing a brand that enables them to better market their territory.

The methodology used, although it provides a general overview of the characteristics of slow tourism, has limitations in addressing the pursued objective. Upon joining the network, cities commit to implementing the slow philosophy, and it is expected that their official websites will disseminate their efforts in this regard. However, local websites do not primarily aim to serve as examples for the global promotion of sustainability.

The analysis conducted in this study, based on the search for evidence on the official websites of Cittaslows, regarding the seven major requirements that, according to the network, slow tourism must meet, shows that they are formally met in most cities, but a more in-depth analysis allows us to affirm that all of them have coherence problems with the slow philosophy.

It cannot be asserted that they truly promote slow, sustainable, and responsible tourism, as they provide information about the distance from the nearest airport, or do not encourage the use of transportation such as bicycles, buses, or trains, which are much less polluting than cars or boats. Additionally, there is no evidence of restrictions on car use in urban centers, except in protected historic areas where the characteristics of medieval urban layout prevent access. There are no Cittaslows that promote the mini- mization of consumption of non-local or nearby products. There is also no news that these cities prohibit the production and/or sale of transgenic products, although they do promote traditional products, especially local gastronomy and craftsmanship. There are no limitations in these cities regarding the opening of fast-food establishments. None of them inform about measures taken to prevent mass tourism and preserve the tranqui- lity of residents, especially in the summer months when all of them become overcrowded. Very few encourage interaction between the local population and visitors, although they do promote accessibility for people with disabilities, as well as environmental well-being and knowledge of local culture. There is not enough news to assert that both tourism agents and companies are collaborating in tourism decision-making. There is no data on the extent to which tourism activities are benefiting the generation of economic benefits for the local population. Despite the above, there is ample evidence that the inclusion of cities in the network is significantly improving their natural and cultural heritage.

All of the above suggests that the governing teams of the Cittaslows should consider acquiring training on the slow philosophy to maintain coherence. The comparison of the results obtained in this

work with those of the study conducted by Maroto et al. (2023), allows us to verify that the recent change in leadership positions in the Spanish Cittaslow network has contributed to improving the information available on the websites of the Cittaslows where they hold the position of mayor.

Sustainable proposal action and future lines of research

At present, sustainability in general and tourism in particular encounter political obstacles rather than technical ones to progress. The aforementioned assertion is evidenced by the absence of reliable indicators in the statistical systems of countries, which would allow us to measure the progress and/or setbacks that are occurring. The significant shortage of environmental indicators contrasts with the considerable number of indicators measuring the economic dimension, and even in the most developed countries, the social dimension. At the international level, we only have indicators for sustainable development, which, as we mentioned at the beginning of this work, barely address tourism specifically and are primarily published at the country level, without descending to the municipal level.

This contrasts with the progress made in recent years in the development of synthetic indicators. This includes those designed for Europe, such as the European Tourism Indicators System (ETIS-2016), or for Spain with the Spanish System of Environmental Indicators for Tourism (SEIAT). There are also indicators at the NUTS 2 level, such as the Sustainable Tourism Development Indicators System of Andalusia.

This leads us to propose a solution that does not entail economic expenditure for the weak local economies of the Cittaslow cities but would substantially improve their image both as sustainable tourist destinations and as examples to be emulated by other cities worldwide. We propose that they include on their official websites, and disseminate through various media, the requirements for excellence that they have met to join the network, which must also be reviewed periodically. These requirements are outlined in the Cittaslow International Charter, and have grown in number over time, with their currently being 73 requirements as of June 2023. Their analysis confirms that they constitute a good information panel (until we have standardized indicators published by the official Statistical Services of all countries), which would allow for the assessment of the quality of the slow destination, including its tourism, as well as the goals it aims to achieve in the coming years. Currently, this information, although each Cittaslow has it, is not published and is not accessible, as would be advisable, for potential tourists to consider when planning their next trip.

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